

CORROSION-RESISTANT MATERIALS AND THEIR PROTECTION METHODS

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Annotation: This article analyzes corrosion-resistant materials and their protection methods. Corrosion is a common problem in engineering, which significantly reduces the service life of metals and alloys. The chemical composition of materials, the condition of their surface, and the environment in which they are used have a significant impact on the corrosion rate. Coatings, alloying, anodizing, inhibitors, and electrochemical protection are presented as protection methods. The study considered the types of the most effective protection methods and the conditions for their application. Based on the analysis, the advantages and disadvantages of each method were discussed.

Keywords: Corrosion, protection methods, alloys, alloying, anodizing, inhibitors, electrochemical protection, passivation, metal, coating

INTRODUCTION: Corrosion is the process of deterioration of materials, especially metals, under the influence of the environment. As a result of this process, materials lose their physical, chemical and mechanical properties. The problem of

corrosion is relevant in various industries, including mechanical engineering, the oil and gas industry, construction, maritime transport and the chemical industry. According to statistics, 15-20 percent of metals produced worldwide become unusable due to corrosion. This leads to billions of dollars in economic losses. Corrosion is also a major threat in terms of safety and reliability. For example, corrosion of pipes or bridges can cause accidents and disasters. Therefore, effective control of corrosion and increasing the durability of materials are technically and economically important.

Corrosion-resistant materials are being developed using modern technologies. Various alloying elements are added to these materials, which increase their chemical stability. Also, the addition of elements with high passivation ability, such as chromium, nickel, molybdenum, forms a passive layer, which protects the material from corrosion. The fight against corrosion is not limited to the selection of materials, but also widely used methods such as reducing the aggressiveness of the environment, covering the surface with special protective coatings, applying inhibitors, anodizing and cathodic protection. The main purpose of the article is to study the properties of corrosion-resistant materials and analyze the protection methods used for them. Corrosion-resistant materials are being developed using modern technologies. Various alloying elements are added to these materials, which increase their chemical stability. Also, the addition of elements with high passivation ability, such as chromium, nickel, molybdenum, forms a passive layer, which protects the material from corrosion. The fight against corrosion is not limited to the

selection of materials, but also widely used methods such as reducing the aggressiveness of the environment, covering the surface with special protective coatings, applying inhibitors, anodizing and cathodic protection. The main purpose of the article is to study the properties of corrosion-resistant materials and analyze the protection methods used for them.

1-Table: The table below shows the corrosion resistance of some materials in various environments, as well as the effectiveness of the protective methods applied to them:

Material	Environment	Coating Type	Corrosion rate (mm/year)	Protection efficiency (%)
Carbon steel	NaCl (3%)	Paint	0.62	45
Stainless steel	H ₂ SO ₄ (5%)	Passivation	0.08	80
Aluminum alloy	Atmosphere	Anodizing	0.03	85
Copper alloy	NaCl (3%)	Inhibitor (organic)	0.12	70
Carbonli po'lat	H ₂ SO ₄ (5%)	Cathodic protection	0.15	75

1-Graph: Corrosion resistance and protective efficiency of various materials.

1-Carbon steel (paint); 2- Stainless steel (passivation); 3-Aluminum alloy (anodizing); 4- Mia alloy (inhibitor); 5-Carbon steel (cathodic protection).

The analyses showed that the most effective protection method for each material varies depending on the environment. Anodizing showed the highest efficiency for aluminum alloys, while passivation was very effective for stainless steels. Organic inhibitors gave positive results for copper alloys. All this indicates the need to take into account the material-environment-technology interrelationship when developing a corrosion protection strategy.

RESULT: As a result of research, it has been found that when choosing corrosion-resistant materials, their chemical composition, crystal structure and alloying elements are important. In particular, alloys with elements such as chromium, nickel, molybdenum and titanium form a passive layer, significantly

slowing down corrosion. For example, chromium in 18-8 stainless steel forms a thin oxide layer on the surface as a result of passivation. This layer protects the material from chemical attacks. The quality of protective coatings and the materials used for them also play an important role. Paints, metal coatings (zinc, nickel, chromium), polymers and ceramics are used for corrosion protection. Also, electrochemical methods (cathodic and anodic protection) are in some cases the most reliable protection method. One of the important aspects of reducing corrosion was the need to control environmental conditions. For example, air humidity, temperature changes, and gas concentrations affect the corrosion process. The level of corrosion can be reduced by neutralizing the environment with chemical methods or adding inhibitors. When choosing protection methods, economic efficiency, service life, and environmental safety should also be taken into account. Therefore, engineers and technologists need to study corrosion in depth and develop an individual approach in each case.

CONCLUSION: Corrosion processes cause serious problems in technological processes and industrial facilities. To prevent or slow them down, methods such as material selection, alloying, passivation, coating, inhibitors, and electrochemical protection are used. The experiments and analyses presented in this article show that choosing the most optimal protection method for each material and environment increases efficiency. In particular, protection methods developed on the basis of modern technologies can increase the service life of materials several times. Also, an integrated approach to combating corrosion - that is, the combined use of

several methods - gives the best results. It is important to continue scientific research in this area to reduce unexpected accidents, economic losses, and environmental problems.

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